

Forest Resources in Himalayan Foothills and Their Appraisal

A Case Study in Kurmai Forest Village

Partha Das[†]
Anirban Roy^{††}

Abstract

The eastern Himalayan foothill region, located to the east of river Tista, is known as 'Dooars' and it bears unique physiography, vegetation and human cultural traits. The vast tropical moist deciduous forest found here, nurtures ample floral and faunal diversity and sustains livelihood of different human tribes. Their culture, economy as well as day to day living have been based on the surrounding forest since ages. With introduction of bureaucratic forest resource management process in the region, modifications have occurred in the life of these forest dwellers. The present study looks into the state of forest resource appraisal by forest dwellers of Dooars region in general and of Chilapata forest reserve and Kurmai village in particular. Along with this, efforts have been made to analyse their level of socio-economic development and hindrances to it.

Keywords

Foothills, Dooars, Cultural Traits, Forest Resource Appraisal, Forest Resource Management, Forest Village

Introduction

The vast tract of land in northern boundary districts of West Bengal, situated at the foothills of the Himalayan Mountain cordillera, built up by the prodigal deposition of sediments by rivers like *Tista*, *Jaldhaka*, *Murti*, *Dayana*, *Torsa* and *Kaljani*, presents a typical landscape that is distinctly different from adjoining mountainous or plain lands of the state. Locally the eastern part of the foothills after River *Tista* is called '*Dooars*,' that means 'gateway' in Bengali. This region served as the entry point to the mountainous country of Bhutan for centuries. The name '*Dooars*' derived from that.

Entire *Dooars* region possess a unique character in terms of its physical conditions and socio-cultural milieu. Situated at the south of the great Himalayan system, this piedmont region receives plenty of rainfall, particularly during Monsoon. Buxa Duar at Alipurduar district is considered as the wettest place in West Bengal. The landscape is undulated, constituted of boulders and recent alluvium carried down by the streams washing the Himalayan slopes. Vegetal growth is abundant as the region bestowed several national parks and reserve forests. Socially the region played a vital role in admixture of different cultural traits from the hills and the plains. Different tribal groups like Toto, Rava, Mech etc. inhabited in Dooars region for centuries in their isolated coves and restricted themselves from admixing with the other tribes. On the other hand there are less conservative Nepalese and Bhutanese people from the hills who have continuously interacted with the tribes of the southern plains like Santhals and Oraons and gave rise to a mixed trait of Madeshia people.

[†]Assistant Professor, Department of Geography, A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar

^{††}Assistant Professor, Department of Geography, Narayangarh Government College, Paschim Medinipur.

Macro-economics of the *Dooars* depend upon three 'T's, i.e. Tea, Timber and Tourism. But the micro-economy playing at the lowest level is, needless to say, subsistence earned through agriculture, forest resource collection and animal husbandry. A large part of daily sustenance of the tribal families, be it food, fodder, house building materials or fuel, comes from the forest. Thus dependence on forest resources for subsistence is high among the inhabitants of villages in and around the forest.

Present study reveals the interaction of the Rava and Oraon people, living in Kurmai village, with the surroundings in the Chilapata Reserve forest in Alipurduar district of West Bengal.

Background of the Study Area

Chilapata forest is actually a range of Jaldapara Wildlife Sanctuary located at the border of Cooch Behar and Alipurduar districts of North Bengal. It is close to Buxa Tiger Reserve and is administered by Cooch Behar Forest Division. Kurmai forest village is located at the south-eastern fringe of Chilapata, couple of hundreds of meters away from the Sonapur – Hasimara road, geographical co-ordinate being 26°31' N and 89°22' E.

The region bears the features of Himalayan foothills and adjacent Barind plains, typical to Dooars. Landform is undulated in the north that gradually merges with rolling plains to the south. Entire region is highly dissected by numerous streams and rivers coming down the slopes of the Himalayas. Rivers have a tendency to change course frequently and they flow through braided channels. Thus shifting river courses gives rise to huge marshy lands. On the other hand, frequent changes in sediment regime lead to unpredictable accumulation of river deposits that are unconsolidated and assorted. Thus the soil type ranges from coarse sands to sandy loam (District Agri. Office, 2003).

Climate is monsoonal with a cold and dry winter and hot and humid summer typical to Himalayan submontane region. Most of the rainfall occurs in the months between June and September. This is one of the wettest places in the West Bengal with average rainfall of 3354 mm. (Directorate of Agriculture, Govt. of WB, 2012). Average temperature varies from 37°C in summer to 5°C in winter. January is the coolest and June is the hottest month in Chilapata and adjacent districts (ibid).

Hot and wet climate facilitated colossal growth of lush green vegetation that is the crown jewel of this part of the earth. Needless to say, once thick and abundant forests are now highly altered by human activities. The region experienced surges of human migration, forest clearing, land reclamation and establishment of new settlements in last hundred years in such a great extent that the lands once infested by wild beasts are now transformed into bustling cities (Chowdhury, 1903).

Chilapata forest has a dense canopy density of about 40 per cent or above in most of the core parts of the forest area. The forest is less dense at the peripheral zones and near the forest villages. The vegetal complex is mostly comprised of Northern Sal, Simul, Khair, Tunn, Moyna, Chap, Arjun, Amiaki, Boyra, Chalta, Amra, Chhatim etc. Tick and Eucalyptus are visible in the peripheral zones where they have been planted by forest department and altered the succession by replacing local varieties. Apart from trees there are numerous species of shrubs, creepers and climbers that grow in abundance and gave the forest a formidable look. Wild animals like Indian Elephant, Gaur, Sambar and other herbivores' from deer family (cervidae) are abundant here. Predators like leopards, foxes

and jackals are common while birds like peacocks, jungle fowl, parrots and hornbills added visual as well as symphonic grandeur to the forest.

There are five forest villages i.e. Andu, Bong, Kurmai, Bania and North Mendabari that surround Chilapata forest range. All of these villages are home to tribal communities who are to some extent isolated from other parts of the district. The survey revealed that Rava is the dominant tribal community in those villages while there is considerable presence of Oraon community also. Most of the villages have both the communities living in segregation while some villages like Anduaru resided exclusively by Rava tribe. Among the five villages, Kurmai is selected for the present case study. It is home for both Rava and Oraon tribes with the former being predominant in population size.

Objectives

Primary objective of the study is to examine the interaction of forest village dwellers to their surrounding forest. Depending on the modes of interaction, some secondary objectives may be identified as follows –

- i) To appreciate the indigenous knowledge base regarding forest resource management.
- ii) To analyse the dependency of the forest dwelling people on forest resources for their subsistence.
- iii) To bring out the perception of the forest dwelling people towards the institutional ways of forest resource management.
- iv) To identify the gap, if any, within the resource perception between forest dwellers and the bureaucracy.
- v) To analyse the community wise socio-economic development of the residents of Kurmai forest village.

Methodology and Data

Extensive field survey had been conducted in Kurmai village with the help of a structured survey schedule. The target was to cover all of the families living in the village. Separate questionnaire had been used for the forest dwellers and forest officials. Apart from the structured schedule, open ended discussions were done with the villagers to understand their perception on the forest, especially its intrinsic values.

The entire work is thoroughly based on primary survey. Of course, secondary data has been utilized as and when required or available. Dearth of secondary data from the part of the forest department possessed serious constraint to the study. To delineate the boundary and location of the village, GPS survey has been conducted.

An array of statistical and cartographic techniques has been considered at the time of data processing. Archived data from National Remote Sensing Centre, India, especially the digital elevation model (DEM) prepared from Cartosat – I with 2.5m spatial resolution and land cover – land use maps prepared from Resourcesat – I with same resolution has been utilised for the study. Graph analysis, pie chart etc. are used for data representation. Microsoft Excel, QGIS, My Map, Google Earth Pro etc. are some software that was useful at data processing.

Results and Discussions

A total of 157 people reside in Kurmai village in 69 households. Among them 49 are Rava families, 19 are Oraon and only one is Goala of Odia origin (fig – 1.1). Average family size is smaller in Rava tribes than in the Oraons (fig – 1.3) and the Ravas have better sex ratio compared to the Oraons (fig – 1.2). All the Oraons believe in Hinduism, so does the sole Goala family of Kurmai. Among the Ravas, almost 95 per cent people adored Christianity while rest of them are still Hindu by faith (fig – 1.4). Residents of Kurmai village are multilingual by nature. There is a great variety of languages spoken in Kurmai. Bengali is the *lingua franca* for the village population but there are languages like Rava, Sadri or Madesia that are community specific. Overall lingual diversity is greater among the Oraon community as they speak as many languages as Sadri, Adivasi, Bengali and Madesia. Rava people are fluent with rava language and Bengali while the Goalas practice Odia along with Bengali (fig – 1.5).

Average literacy rate of Kurmai village is 85 per cent, which is well above the state and district averages of 76.3% and 73.3% respectively (Census – 2011). Again, Rava community in Kurmai have higher percentage of literacy rate than the Oraons (fig – 2.1).

People in Kurmai are educationally backward. Most of the adult population are either just literate or primary educated. Educational status is better in younger generations and a few of them are pursuing higher education. Though the Oraon community in Kurmai have larger percentage of illiterate population, but at the same time they have greater number of people who have completed secondary level school education (fig – 2.3). All of the families in Kurmai reported occurrence of school dropout. The reason varies from poverty, early marriage in women to lack of access and lack of interest (fig – 2.2). Notably, there is no primary school in Kurmai. The nearest one is located at Mathurapur, some five kilometres from the village. Secondary and higher secondary schools are also located there. Nearest college from the village is in Hasimara town that is located some 21 km away from Kurmai. Thus it is evident that pursuing education from Kurmai is not easy, especially considering the location of the village in a remote forest clad area.

LOCATION OF THE STUDY AREA

Source: Google Earth Pro, My Map and various websites

I. DEMOGRAPHIC SCENARIO: KURMAI VILLAGE

Source: Primary Survey

2. LITERACY STATUS AND LEVEL OF EDUCATION: KURMAI VILLAGE

Source: Primary Survey

Almost 80 per cent families from both tribes belong to Below Poverty Level (BPL). Most of the Kurmai residents depend on primary economic activities for their livelihood. Agriculture, forest products collection and animal husbandry are the three main sectors of primary activity that engage 77 per cent of the workforce of the village. Forest related subsistence comprises at least 19 per cent of the population though several other economic activities are also indirectly related with the forest resources. Share of two communities are almost equal in economic sectors like agriculture and forest resource collection. Ravas are better engaged in animal husbandry, business and also with the forest department and other government jobs. While a meagre percentage of the Oraon people works as drivers and daily wage labourers. (Fig -3.1).

3. OCCUPATIONAL STRUCTURE: KURMAI VILLAGE

House building materials and building techniques reflects the cultural differences between two tribal communities living side by side. Majority of the houses in Kurmai village are permanent in nature, although there are some semi-permanent hutments near the forest fringe that are probably freshly

built on encroached forest land. Almost sixty per cent houses are 'pucca' constructions. Ravas are in better condition than the Oraon community in this regard. Most of the houses are single storied with some exception of two-storied buildings owned by some Rava families (fig -4.1). Roofing material is same for the two communities. Ignoring the negligible percentage of concrete roof houses, it is corrugated steel or aluminium sheets that are the most preferred roofing material (fig -4.2). A sharp contrast in community centric indigenous engineering is reflected in the structure, built and material used for wall. Rava houses are more likely to be built on raised wooden platforms where wood is the construction material for walls. These houses have some arrangement of ladder or wooden staircase to reach the platform. Often the ground floor is loosely covered up from the sides by corrugated iron sheets to provide shelter for the domestic animals or to keep the harvest. On the other hand all of the Oraon houses are built on the ground using mud or metal sheets as the wall construction material. They keep animals and grains in separate shades, generally made from lesser quality materials. There are also some brick built houses in Kurmai, most of them belonging to Rava community (fig -4.3).

Open defecation is still prevalent in Kurmai village, especially among the Oraons. At least 35 per cent of Oraon families do not have any toilet facility within their premises. A community toilet for the Oraons has been installed in 2016 by the local Mathura Panchayet in Kurmai to change this habit. Among the Ravas, open defecation is practiced by 22 per cent families. Although some admitted receipt of grant for construction of toilets from the Gram Panchayat, still lots of effort is required to stop this unhygienic practice (fig -4.4).

People of Kurmai use both ground water and surface water for household use and drinking purpose. There are only three community tube wells with limited capacity to serve the entire village population. Two of the tube wells are installed by the Gram Panchayat while the other is maintained by the Church. Communities have segregated their source of potable water, thus Oraon community use one tube well in their vicinity and Ravas use the other two. Thus there are some households that have to fetch drinking water from a distance more than 300 meters. There is a small non-perennial stream coming out of the forest near the gateway of Kurmai village. This unnamed stream serves as the source of domestic water for a considerable population of the village. At least 36 per cent of Oraon families and 11 per cent of Rava families depend on this source for their daily household water needs including the drinking water (fig -4.5).

Fuel use pattern reveals that villagers of Kurmai are still very much dependent on biomass and most of that comes from nearby forests. Use of fossil fuels in kitchen is restricted to slightly better offs. Dead leafs, dry twigs and branches and fuel wood collected from the forest in Chilapata range are the major source of energy in the kitchens of most of the households in Kurmai. No families use coal as fuel while a few use kerosene. LPG is used by only eighteen families in Kurmai. Among them, one family is from Oraon community while the rest are Ravas. In general Ravas in Kurmai are in higher position in the social ladder of fuel utilization (fig -4.7).

One third of the households in Kurmai got electricity. Majority of these houses belongs to Rava community. So is the scenario for the other household amenities like TV, dish antenna and refrigerator. Mobile phone is used by 33percent families in Kurmai and again most of the families belong to Rava community. There are 7 families that possess motor bike and six of them are Rava. The sole owner of car and tractor in the village is a Rava family (fig -4.6).

4. HOUSE BUILDING MATERIALS AND AVAILABLE FACILITIES: KURMAI VILLAGE

Fig. - 4.1

Fig. - 4.2

Fig. - 4.3

Fig. - 4.4

Fig. - 4.5

Fig. - 4.6

Fig. - 4.7

Source: Primary Survey

Perception on Forest Resources

People living in Kurmai village consider the presence of Chilapata forest in the vicinity of their village as a boon, not a hindrance. Both the communities have lived in forestlands for generations and they have an inseparable bond with it that is well depicted in their material and non-material, cultural as well as in their everyday activities.

Oraon people present in Himalayan foothills in general and Kurmai in particular had their origin in the Chhotanagpur plateau of present day Jharkhand. It is the ability of the Oraon people to survive in the forest environment that had attracted the colonial rulers to relocate them in large groups to foothill

region in order to reclaim land for tea plantation and other agricultural activities. Still now they practice animism where forest plays a vital role. Though the Oraon people living in Kurmai consider themselves as Hindu, still they worship 'Dharmesh' the almighty, *Biri* or the Sun, (*hanch*) or the Moon and *Dharti Aayo* or the mother Earth. All of the religious activities that are called '*Sarama*' are performed under the sacred grooves (Ghosh, 2001).

Rava tribe is aboriginal to Goalpara and Kamrup district of Assam. They have been living in the Himalayan foothills since time immemorial. Ravas have migrated to West Bengal and Meghalaya from their places of origin in later time. They have confined themselves within the natural boundary of Terai-Dooars region. In West Bengal they are found in three districts i.e. Jalpaiguri, Alipurduar and Cooch Behar. These Indo-Mongoloid people had close connection with the Koch kingdom in Cooch Behar (Mitra, 1953). Rava tribe was historically dependant on the forest as they practiced shifting cultivation in small groups along the sub-Himalayan region. Changing socio-political scenario of the foothills forced them to adopt with the changing landscape and emerge as a partly agricultural-partly labourer tribe. Their strong affinity to forests was adored by the planters in colonial times and thus they are most prominent tribal group in the Dooars region. Although most of the Rava families in Kurmai village embraced Christianity but that didn't stop them to practice their age-old traditional animistic rituals. They worship *Rishi* or *Mahakal* as the almighty. '*Mahakal*' in Rava language also stands for the elephant. Thus they believe that the harmony in nature must be restrained in order to sustain human life in a healthy way (Karlsson, 2000).

Dependence on Forest Resources

All of the families living in Kurmai village, be it Rava or be it Oraon, have similar kind of dependence on the forest resource for their daily livelihood. They depend on the nearby Chilapata forest for small woods for the preparation of agricultural tools, logs and poles for the construction of houses etc. Present survey had identified four major sectors of livelihood that are almost exclusively dependant on the forest resources i.e. fodder, fuel, building materials and medicine.

Kurmai had a large cattle population. Ravas generally rear cow, goat and sheep while Oraons rear pigs in addition. Fowl and duck are also popular as domestic source of protein. The entire cattle population of Kurmai browse on the forest land adjacent to the village. There are abundance of grass and green leaves in the forest that can thrive the famish cattle population of the village even in the dry winter. Thus the dairy farming, meat production, wool production and other animal husbandry related income generation in the village are thoroughly dependant on the forest resources.

At least sixty per cent of the daily fuel demand in Kurmai is supplemented by the Chilapata forest. Villagers collect dead leaves, dry twigs and branches of the trees from the forest floor and burn them into their earthen ovens to prepare their daily food. Forest department issues permits for cutting dead or dry trees from the forest to the villagers. Thus wood is one of the important sources of fuel in Kurmai (fig. 4.7). There is a sharp economic discrimination within the users of biomass as fuel in Kurmai. Economically downtrodden families, those who belong to the lowest step of socio-economic ladder are the sole users of dry leaves and twigs while the relatively better-offs have the access to the fuel wood. This is most prominent among the Oraon people in Kurmai, though less acute, also evident among the Ravas.

Wooden planks, poles and bars are the most sorted out building material for the Ravas in kurmai village. Ravas have a tradition to build their home on elevated platforms that is connected with the

ground by a staircase. Both of them are made by the wood collected from the nearby forest. Planks are used as flooring and wall material. Wooden bars and poles hold the roof over the walls. Though in present days corrugated metal sheets are substituting wood as roof and wall building material very fast, still there are many Rava homes in Kurmai that are entirely made of wood and ornately designed in traditional way (fig.- 4.2 and 4.3). Unlike the Ravas, Oraons are less dependent on the forest for their home. They usually build mud houses with thatched roofs. Still they need poles and bars as well as wood for making doors and windows. They use hey and straw as roof material. All wood sheet houses are getting popularity now a day, thus reducing the dependency on the forest for woods and releasing the pressure on the forest resources as well.

Rava and Oraon people are endowed with rich heritage of traditional knowledge of herbal medicine. Chilapata forest range, according to some villagers, is an endless source of roots, shoots, herbs, barks, leaves, flowers and fruits with medicinal qualities. Some of them are listed below with their medicinal values (Table 1). Another important aspect is that the tribal people still prefer these herbs over modern medicine when they are sick. Although they have admitted that this preference is in decadence, precisely among the youth.

Table 1: Some Medicinal Plants of Chilapata Forest with their Utilization

Sl. No.	Local Name	Scientific Name	Parts Used	Ailment Treated
1.	Amlaki/Amla	<i>Phyllanthusemblica</i>	Fruit (whole)	Cold and cough Stomach ailment
2.	Amra	<i>Spondiasmombin</i>	Fruit	Stomach ailment
	Anatamul	<i>Hemisdemusindicus</i>	Root	Blood purifier, antitoxic, skin eruption, arthritis.
3.	Arjun	<i>Terminaliaarjuna</i>	Bark	Lung related diseases.
4.	Basak	<i>Justiciaadhatoda</i>	leaf	Cold, Rhinitis
5.	Bel	<i>Aeglemarmelos</i>	Fruit, leaf	Cholera, gastric ulcer, antimicrobial.
6.	Boyera	<i>Terminaliabellicrica</i>	Fruit	Cold and Cough, leaver ailment, constipation
7.	Chattiya	<i>Alstoniascholaris</i>	bark	Irregular period
8.	Durba	<i>Cynodondactylon</i>	Whole	Cut, burn, fever
9.	Dudhilata	<i>Oxistelmaesculata</i>	Plant	Urinary tract infection
10.	Ghetu	<i>Clerodendroninfortunatum</i>	Flower	Intestinal worms, colic diarrhea, skin disease
11.	Haritaki	<i>TerminaliaChebula</i>	Fruit	Indigestion, constipation, skin problem, diabetes
12.	Junglee Pan	---	Fruit extract	Cold and cough in children
13.	Kalmegh	<i>Andrographispanniculata</i>	Stem, leaf	Intestinal worms, sinusitis, body pain.
14.	Kul	<i>Ziziphys jujube</i>	Fruit, seed	Anti-oxidant, immunity booster, sedative
15.	Kurchi	<i>Holarrhaenaantidycenterica</i>	Bark	Dysentery, blood related disorders
16.	Neem	<i>Azadirachtaindica</i>	Leaf, Seed	Leprosy, intestinal worms, skin ulcers, gum disease
17.	Pepe	<i>Carica papaya</i>	Fruit, gum	Stomach pain, loose motion
18.	Sarpagandga	<i>Rainwolfiasarperntina</i>	Rhizome, Root	High Blood sugar, insomnia, hypertension
19.	Satamul	<i>Asparagus racemosa</i>	Root	Ulcer, constipation, diarrhea.
20.	Seuli	<i>Nyctanthesarbortristis</i>	Root, Seed, leaf	Arthritis, constipation, sciatica
21.	Somraj	<i>Vernoniaantheimintica</i>	Root	Medicine
22.	Shimul	<i>Bombaxcebia</i>	Sapling root	Stomach ailment and constipation
23.	Surimara	---	Flower bark	Hepatitis White discharge in women
24.	Thankuni	<i>Centellaasiatica</i>	leaf	Leaver ailment, Amibiosis
25.	Tulsi	<i>Ocimumtenuiflorum</i>	leaf	Skin diseases, lung and throat diseases

Source: Primary Survey and Forest Directorate, Government of West Bengal, 1997

Perception on Forest Management

Indian National Forest Policy of 1988 ensured participation of forest dwellers in the forest management process through Joint forest management (JFM). It was implemented through Forest Protection Committees (FPC) those were constructed in the forest ranges throughout India to ensure participation of the forest dwelling people in the forest management system (Kumar, 2001). There is a FPC in Kurmai village that take care of a part of Chilapata forest range. According to the

participating villagers, the FPC in Kurmai was almost non-functional due to some political unrest until recent past. There was difference of opinion regarding profit sharing among the participant families. Recently, in 2013, the FPC was reinstated and is now in functioning condition. All the member families received high capacity flash lights from the forest department in the month of November, 2017 that will facilitate night patrols and chasing invading animals, especially elephant herds from the village boundary.

Villagers of Kurmai complained about the elitist behaviour of the forest officials regarding the forest management planning process that comes in purview of the FPC. They receive cold behaviour from the government side when they apply for the permits to extract forest resources. Moreover, high-handedness of a section of the forest officials made the villages felt themselves outsider in the place where they are the legitimate stakeholders. Thus, a process of alienation gradually is crippling the participatory management of the forest resources in Chilapata range. Moreover this feeling of 'otherness' is leading to increasing conflicts between the forest villages and the forest officials regarding lesser forest product collection.

Another issue that should be taken care of is the unplanned and uncontrolled growth of tourism activities in and around Chilapata forest region. Several so-called eco-tourism resorts and home stays have been developed in and around Kurmai village. It seems that forest department or village *panchayat* or any other government body do not have any monitoring mechanism to ensure the interest of the wildlife and local people. Some of the villages do get benefited by leasing out their lands to the developers and some people gained as tourist guides and vehicle drivers, but they are negligible in number. Villagers complained about the erratic behaviour of the tourists, their love to loud music and alcohol abuse that have left a derogatory impact on the local youth as well as the wild life of the region.

Findings

Major findings of the present study may be summarised as the following –

- i. Kurmai forest village is resided by two tribal communities of different origin i.e. Rava and Oraon.
- ii. Two communities share the same natural resources but live in almost complete social segregation. No socio-cultural exchanges have been observed.
- iii. Both Rava and Oraon communities are educationally and economically backward. Though Ravas are slightly better-off in this regard as compared to their counterparts.
- iv. Two communities display distinct differences in material culture, particularly in traditional engineering methods. But both of them depend similarly on natural resources, especially the forest for the purpose.
- v. Instead of differences in material culture, two communities practice animism beside their hegemonic religious identities and forest plays a huge role in those cultural practices.
- vi. Forest resource collection is the second most important pillar of their daily livelihood, after agriculture.
- vii. Across the communities, residents of Kurmai village depend on the forest resources in four major sectors, i.e. fodder, fuel, construction materials and medicine.

- viii. Both of the communities possess profound knowledge in traditional medicine. They still prefer traditional medicines over the modern one.
- ix. Forest management through FPC is in a cross-road in Kurmai. Difference of opinion on profit sharing between the participating families and the forest department almost paralysed its normal function.
- x. Villagers' faces blues regarding issuance of forest resource collection permits. Some cases of conflict between the forest guards and local residents have been reported in recent time.

Conclusion

Like every tribal forest village in India, Kurmai possess some uniqueness regarding its interface with the natural resources, forest resources in particular. At the same time there are same old problems of bureaucratic interference in the form of top-down planning from the part of the Government officials. Elitist exposition of power by the forest department and sometimes inability of the local tribal people to address the emerging issues regarding forest resource management is gradually widening the rift between the stakeholders in Chilapata forest range. The age-old traditional knowledge of the forest dwellers like the Ravas and Oraons in Kurmai village can be recognised as a tool of effective forest resource management. Forest department should take initiative in this matter, otherwise the whole objective of the joint forest management will be jeopardised in Chilapata forest range.

Acknowledgement

This project was financially supported by Acharya Brojendra Nath Seal College Parent-Teacher Association. The authors heartily thank A.B.N.S.C.P.T.A. for their continuous support. The authors are also thankful to the teachers, support staff and especially the students of Geography Department of A.B.N Seal College for their help in various ways during the project.

Works cited

- Chowdhury H.N, 1903: The Cooch Behar State and its Land Revenue Settlement. Cooch Behar State Press. Cooch Behar, India.
- Directorate of Agriculture, 2012: District Agricultural Report, Cooch Behar. Government of West Bengal. Kolkata.
- District Agricultural Officer, 2003: Annual departmental report (unpublished). Department of Agriculture. Government of West Bengal. Cooch Behar.
- Ghosh A. (2003): History and culture of Oraon tribe; some aspects of their social life. Mohit Publication. Delhi. P. 237
- Karlsson B G (2000): Contested Belonging: An indigenous people's struggle for forest and identity in Sub-Himalayan Bengal. Psychology Press. London
- Kumar H.D, 2001: Forest resources: Conservation and management; Affiliated east- west Publication Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi, pp. 1 – 228.
- Mitra A (1953): West Bengal District Hand book; Jalpaiguri. Government of West Bengal. Kolkata

VICTORIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS

ISSN: 0975-5632

Vol. XI Issue I

January 2018

UGC Enlisted Journal No. 41277

BOARD OF ADVISORS

Ratanlal Chakraborty, Former Professor, Department of History, University of Dhaka

Nrisingha Prasad Bhaduri, Eminent Professor of Sanskrit and Writer

Ananda Gopal Ghosh, Former Professor, Department of History, University of North Bengal

Bimal Kumar Saha, Officer-in-Charge, A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

Debabrata Lahiri, Associate Professor, Department of Economics,
A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar

MANAGING EDITOR

Shampa Dutta, Assistant Professor, Department of Political Science,
A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar

EDITORIAL BOARD

Samir Kr. Samanta, Associate Professor, Department of Geography, A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar

Debasis Mallik, Associate Professor, Department of Bengali, A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar

Prajnaparamita Sarkar, Associate Professor, Department of History, A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar

Amrita Ghosh, Assistant Professor, Department of Sanskrit, A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar

Ratul Ghosh, Assistant Professor, Department of Bengali, A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar

Debapratim Chakraborty, Assistant Professor, Department of English, A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar

Sutapa Chakraborty, Assistant Professor, Department of Philosophy, A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar

PUBLISHER

Office of the Principal, A.B.N. Seal College, Cooch Behar; P.O. & Dist. Cooch Behar, West
Bengal, PIN 736101

Contents

The Origin, Development and Varieties of the Aniconic Forms of Śaiva Iconography in the Indian Subcontinent Arka Acharjee	1
The Boundary Demarcation Between India and East Pakistan: The Problem of Adverse Possession in South Berubari of Jalpaiguri Sudash Lama, Biswajit Kar	11
The Historical Aspect of the Vienna Congress: The Beginning of the 100 Year Peace Rajeshree Dutta	20
Forest Resources in Himalayan Foothills and Their Appraisal: A Case Study in Kurmai Forest Village Partha Das, Anirban Roy	26
Marginalisation and Gender: A Study on the Position of Hijras in Religion, Society and State in India Ruman Sutradhar	38
On the Nature and Limits of Knowledge: A Critical Assessment of Locke's View Mrinal Kanti Basak	47
Newton's Three Laws of Motion as Judgments of Experience in Kant Eagam Khaling	52
The Phenomenological Given-ness of the Subjective: An Approach after Edmund Husserl Sutapa Chakraborty	58
Navya Nyāya Theory of Indeterminate Perception Riki Chakraborty	62
Related Party Information: An Analysis of Corporate Practices in India Sanjoy Kumar Roy, Uttam Kumar Dutta, Subrata Kar	66
সুরাসুরপ্রসঙ্গ : বেদের নিরিখে অদিতি ভট্টাচার্য	74
আধুনিক বিজ্ঞান ও সনাতন ভারতবর্ষীয় আধ্যাত্মিক শাস্ত্রানুযায়ী পৃথিবীর ক্রমবিকাশের তুলনামূলক আলোচনা ও আরও কিছু কথা বিমল কুমার সাহা	77
ভারতীয় ধর্মনিরপেক্ষতার সাম্প্রতিক সংকট এবং তার রাজনৈতিক বৈধতা বিশ্বনাথ সরকার	87
প্রশাসনে স্বচ্ছতা ও দায়বদ্ধতা প্রতিষ্ঠায় তথ্যের অধিকার আইন ২০০৫ : করণদীর্ঘি ব্লকের একটি গ্রামীণ বাস্তবতা নরোত্তম বিশ্বাস	93
সাহিত্যভাবনার অন্য বিশ্বায়ন : মোহিতলালের বিবেচনায় বাঙালির রোম্যান্টিক সাহিত্য দিব্যতনু দাশগুপ্ত	101
'ছন্নছাড়া' : মধ্যবিত্ত ভদ্রতার মুখে চপেটাঘাত শান্তনু মন্ডল	107